

Survival Study on Energy Aware Routing and Secured Data Aggregation in Wireless Sensor Network

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ABSTRACT

Wireless sensor network (WSN) is used to sense and collect the information in a specific region and sent to the base station (BS). Energy efficiency is the major issue in WSNs that addressed through routing methods. However, the routing protocols failed to transmit the data packets in secured manner. Energy efficient routing is the method of utilizing the less energy during routing task. Secured data transmission is carried out to preserve the data packets from the illegal access, damage, or disruption. Data aggregation collects the useful information with minimum lesser energy consumption. Secured data aggregation process preserves the collected data packets against different security attacks. Many classification and blockchain methods were introduced for performing efficient and secured data aggregation in WSN. But, the energy consumption was not reduced and data confidentiality was not improved by existing techniques. In order to address these issues, different machine learning and cryptographic methods are introduced for secured data transmission in WSN.

Keywords: wireless sensor network, energy efficient routing, secured data transmission, secured data aggregation, data confidentiality

1. INTRODUCTION

Wireless sensor network (WSN) is used to provide different benefits like low-power smart computation, compact size, self organizing and ability to route via routing protocols. WSN is used for different home automation, smart cities, fire detection,

unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) and object tracking. Sensor nodes are small and battery operated one from fundamental restrictions like available bandwidth, memory space, power constraints and inadequate resources. WSN addressed the energy optimization and secure data communication to improve the network lifetime and to defend against malicious nodes. The clustering methods are smart and effective approach to minimize the energy consumption and extend network lifetime.

WSN comprised small sensor nodes with limited energy to monitor physical conditions and communicate to other nodes without any physical medium. WSN is more susceptible to security threats because of random node deployment in network. Accordingly, WSN cause security issues in network that affects the communication. Data aggregation is the process of summarizing the data collection and reducing data size during transmission. The data aggregation is the process of gathering the information from its neighboring sensor nodes and transmits to the base station through routing topology. The energy consumed by transmitting and receiving data through sensor nodes gets reduced.

The main contribution of the survey article is given as:

- To study the energy efficient routing methods in wireless sensor network for increasing the network lifetime of the network
- To discuss different secured data transaction methods of wireless sensor networks with higher accuracy level
- To compare different secured data aggregation approaches for attaining better result with minimum time consumption.

The contents of this paper are organized as follows: Section 1 presents the introduction to energy efficient and secured data routing in WSN. Section 2 presents the review of various methods for energy efficient and secured data aggregation in wireless sensor network. Section 3 explains the description of methodology for energy efficient and secured data aggregation with neat diagram. Section 4 explains energy efficient routing

with different performance metrics. Section 5 describes the secured data transaction methods with performance metrics. Section 6 explains the secured data aggregation methods with the performance metrics. Section 7 concludes the review work.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

An energy-efficient coverage method was introduced in [1] for wireless sensor network nodes to increase the energy efficiency and data transmission reliability. Every monitoring point was covered by one sensor node through energy-saving sensor network node coverage model. But, the designed energy-efficient coverage method was limited by the experimental scale and failed to cover all potential scenarios of large-scale network.

A hierarchical and distributed approach was introduced in [2] with low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) algorithm and analytic hierarchy process (AHP). The designed approach preserved the matrix within nodes representing the probability of node. But, hierarchical and distributed approach failed to minimize the computational load.

An innovative PRE scheme was introduced in [3] for WSNs to perform secured communication between nodes within network and data server. The designed scheme preserved the sensor-node data encryption and assigned re-encryption tasks for improving the data privacy and integrity. But, innovative PRE scheme failed to address the resource-constrained problems in WSNs, for exploring real-world deployment scenarios.

A clustering approach was introduced in [4] depending on data aggregation process for hierarchical structuring. The aggregation process was carried out with nodes in cluster using uniform distribution. But, the designed clustering approach failed to construct lifetime and latency-aware clusters with routing tree through considering link quality.

A low-energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) was introduced in [5] to efficiently perform data transfer. Fuzzy logic and artificial neural networks (ANNs) were

introduced for intrusion detection systems (IDS). But, advanced protocol was not employed to efficiently transfer data.

An Improved Buffalo Optimized Route Selective Deep Feed Forward Neural Learning (IBORSDFFNL) Model was introduced in [6] to construct the multiple paths for efficient data aggregation in WSN. Though data packet delivery ratio was improved, the security remained unaddressed by using IBORSDFFNL Model.

An energy aware and secure routing (EASR) was introduced in [7] for hierarchical cluster based WSN. LEACH with improved threshold value was employed to choose the secure optimal CH and trust based routing model. However, the machine learning techniques was not used to analyze comprehensive trust value to reduce the computation overhead.

A new light weighted key distribution mechanism was designed in [8] for energy efficient communication in WSN. Coot updated Butterfly algorithm with Logistic Solution Space algorithm (CUBA-LSS) was employed for optimal clustering through choosing the optimal CH. But, the light weighted key distribution mechanism was not utilized for real-time datasets and not prioritized memory issue.

A lightweight Secure Aggregation and Transmission Scheme (SATS) was designed in [9] for secure and lightweight data computation and transmission. SATS preserved against security threats like denial of service attacks, man in the middle attack, and reply attacks. But, the processing time was not minimized by SATS.

A trust-based optimized clustered routing method termed Trust Index Optimized Cluster Head Routing (TIOCHR) algorithm was introduced in [10] for Cluster Head (CH) selection. The trustworthy potential paths were selected for improving the reliability and integrity. But, TIOCHR algorithm performance was not improved by using mobile nodes.

A memetic algorithm was introduced in [11] to identify the optimal routing paths through reducing energy consumption and increasing data delivery ratio. The designed

algorithm increased the network performance metrics with higher lifespan and data reliability. But, the computational cost was not reduced by memtic algorithm.

Energy Saving and Securing Data algorithm (ESSD) algorithm was introduced in [12] to present Message Digest 5 (MD5) computation through varying power consumption condition. ESSD increased the security and reduced power consumption. But, the security level was not at required level by ECC and MD5 with ESSD algorithm.

A new blockchain with Enhanced Hunger Games Search based Route Planning (BCEHGS-RP) scheme was introduced in [13] for WSN. BCEHGS-RP model used BC technology for secured data communication in WSN. However, BCEHGS-RP scheme failed to combine data aggregation and compression systems for improving longevity of the network.

Secure and load balanced routing (SLBR) scheme was introduced in [14] for heterogeneous clustered based WSNs. SLBR provided the trust-based security metric for oscillating from good to bad state. However, the designed scheme failed to consider the network parameters for detecting different kind of attacks.

An innovative multi-objective routing protocol termed multi-objective chaotic Boltzmann ant colony optimization routing protocol (MO-CBACORP) was introduced in [15] to reduce the energy consumption of sensor nodes in UMWSN routing.. But, MO-CBACORP failed to determine the underwater sensor mobility on system with varying topological structures.

An environment-fusion multipath routing protocol (EFMRP) was introduced in [16] for improved message forwarding service. EFMRP approach transmitted the data packets to select the routes with minimum latency, energy conservation and routing. But, the energy consumption was not reduced by EFMRP.

Improvised Energy Efficient Multipath ACO based Routing Protocol (IEEMARP) was introduced in [17] for WSN. The designed protocol neighbor discovery, packet

transmission and packet delivery for end-to-end data delivery. Though packet delivery ratio was improved, the delay was not reduced by IEEMARP.

The routing scheme was introduced in [18] to perform the cooperation among path with bridge node. It prevented the transmission failure and delay packet transmission issues on path. Though the delay was reduced, the packet delivery ratio was not improved by routing scheme.

A secure multipath routing protocol was introduced in [19] for mission and safety systems. An efficient lightweight privacy preserving authentication technique improved the security level and privacy. But, the computational cost was not reduced by secure multipath routing protocol.

An energy-efficient routing protocol was introduced in [20] for IoT application in network. The designed protocol employed three-factor to select the optimal path at next-hop node. However, the routing overhead was not reduced through energy efficient routing protocol.

An optimized Elliptic Curve Cryptographic (ECC) technique termed IECC was designed in [21] for secured communication against different attacks. But, IECC technique failed to reduce energy consumption model and to enhance the network lifetime. A secure routing method was introduced in [22] for secure data aggregation through avoiding the intrusion of malicious nodes. However, encryption method was not used to improve the security with minimal overhead.

Secure data aggregation protocol was introduced in [23] to improve the information security through identifying the Denial of Service (DOS) attacks. However, energy-efficient data aggregation remained the key problem. Improved Blowfish algorithm (IBFA) was introduced in [24] for secured authentication. However, the cluster based secure data transmission was not performed to reduce the delay. Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) method was introduced in [25] for increasing the energy efficiency and data security. However, the delay performance was not reduced by ECC method.

3. METHODOLOGY

Wireless sensor networks (WSN) not have any particular infrastructure. WSN comprised number of sensor nodes to monitor environmental condition for data collection. The sensors are small with computing resources. WSN is used to sense, measure and collect the information from environment depending on local decision process. WSN transmit the sensed data to the user. Security and sensor node lifetime in network plays an important role. Reliable data transfer between sensor nodes and efficient data transmission to the collecting station (i.e., base station is an essential problem in WSN). Secured routing plays important role to address the data confidentiality and data integrity problems. The process used for secured data transaction and data aggregation in WSN is given in the figure 1.

Figure 1 Architecture Diagram of Resource Efficient and Secured Data Aggregation in WSN

Figure 1 explains the architecture diagram of resource efficient and secured data aggregation in WSN. The sensor nodes are considered as an input. The energy level and security level of sensor nodes are computed for performing resource efficient and secured data aggregation in WSN.

4. RESOURCE EFFICIENT ROUTING IN WSN

Wireless sensor networks (WSNs) comprised the number of sensor nodes for tracking, measuring and monitoring different phenomena. The sensor nodes are operated under different resource constraints. Different algorithms are used to address the power consumption and processing demands for WSNs. Energy-efficient routing is carried out through minimizing the energy consumption in WSNs during communication phase. An energy-efficient routing technique becomes imperative one to address the energy consumption problems and increased the network lifetime.

4.1 Energy Efficient Node Coverage Model

An energy-efficient coverage method is introduced in wireless sensor network for increasing the energy efficiency and data transmission reliability. By using hierarchical and flat routing protocols, every monitoring point is wrapped by at least one sensor node by energy-saving sensor network node coverage model. An energy-efficient coverage method was introduced depending on the improved gray wolf algorithm to optimize the deployment of sensor nodes and to improve the node coverage. Energy-saving wireless sensor network models are employed to address the needs of future intelligent monitoring and control. The designed network method increased the resource utilization efficiency, minimize the maintenance cost and improve the sustainable development of WSN. Energy-efficient coverage method addressed the energy efficiency problems improving network coverage and transmission efficiency. An advanced optimization algorithms

handled the node energy consumption problems and improved coverage of monitoring area.

4.2 Hierarchical and Distributed Approach

A new hierarchical and distributed approach is introduced to join the low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) algorithm with analytic hierarchy process (AHP). The designed approach maintained the matrix within nodes. The designed approach comprised the threshold values with node probability of becoming cluster head (CH). The values in matrix are linked with the energy and distance conditions of sensor nodes. The energy level and distance to the sink node were taken as criteria in the AHP method. The probability of node becoming the CH is determined using AHP with different levels varying from 1 to 9 depending on the energy and distance criterion. The energy criterion over distance is weighted with 3, 5, and 7. The threshold values for energy and distance scenarios are obtained through AHP. The designed approach reduced the energy consumption and increased the number of packets transmitted to the sink node. The designed method authorized the nodes to decide their probability of becoming CH depending on the energy status and distance to sink node without centralized control.

4.3 Improved Buffalo Optimized Deep Feed Forward Neural Learning

Improved Buffalo Optimized Route Selective Deep Feed Forward Neural Learning (IBORSDFFNL) Model is designed to construct the multiple paths for efficient data aggregation in the wireless sensor networks. IBORSDFFNL Model performed route path discovery and optimal route path selection process. The multiple route paths are built from the distributed sensor nodes. Among route path construction, an optimal route path is selected through improved buffalo optimization for efficient data aggregation in the WSN. After choosing the efficient optimal route path, the data aggregation process is performed with lesser delay and higher packet delivery ratio. The designed IBORSDFFNL Model attained lesser energy consumption and end-to-end delay for energy-efficient data transmission and improve the packet delivery ratio in WSNs.

4.4 Performance Metrics for Resource Efficient Data Routing in WSN

The two performance metrics employed for resource efficient data routing is energy consumption and network lifetime. Energy consumption is defined as the amount of energy consumed by sensor nodes during sensing and data transmission. This measurement is expressed in joules (J).

$$E_c = \sum_{i=1}^n S n_i * EC (OSN) \quad (1)$$

From (1), ' E_c ' denotes the energy consumption, ' n ' indicates the number of sensor nodes. ' $E_c(OSN)$ ' denotes energy consumption for one sensor node. The second metric is network lifetime. The network lifetime of the sensor node is computed as the ratio of initial energy of the node to the energy consumption per data transmission. It is formulated as,

$$Nk_{lf} = \left[\frac{E_I}{E_{tr}} \right] \quad (2)$$

From (2), ' Nk_{lf} ' denotes the network lifetime of sensor nodes. ' E_I ' symbolizes the initial energy of sensor nodes. ' E_{tr} ' denotes the energy consumption of sensor node for data transmission. It is computed in terms of seconds (S). When network lifetime is lesser, the method is said to be more efficient.

Table 1 Tabulation for Energy Consumption and Network Lifetime for Resource Efficient Routing in WSN

Parameters/ Methods	Energy Consumption (J)	Network Lifetime (s)
Energy-efficient coverage method	89	0.268
New hierarchical and distributed approach	51	0.873
IBORSDFNL Model	0.04	5.4

Figure 2 Measurement Analysis of Energy Consumption and Network Lifetime

Figure 2 illustrates the measurement analysis of energy consumption and network lifetime for three different existing methods, namely energy-efficient coverage method, new hierarchical and distributed approach and IBORSDFNL Model. From the above graphical analysis, the red color column represents the network lifetime of three different methods and green color column symbolizes the energy consumption of three different methods. The performance of IBORSDFNL Model is higher than other two techniques. This is due to the application Coot updated Butterfly algorithm with Logistic Solution Space algorithm (CUBA-LSS) for optimal clustering through choosing the optimal CH. Lightweight key management system preserved the encryption key. The energy consumption of IBORSDFNL Model is reduced by 99% and 99% when compared to the energy-efficient coverage method, new hierarchical and distributed approach respectively. The network lifetime of IBORSDFNL Model is increased by 98% and 38% when compared to the energy-efficient coverage method and new hierarchical and distributed approach respectively.

5. SECURED DATA TRANSACTION IN WSN

Secured data transaction is the process of transmitting the data packets from the source sensor node to the destination sensor node in secured manner. Different security methods are used to preserve the data packets from unauthorized users. Secured data transaction methods are used to increase the data confidentiality and data integrity in wireless sensor networks.

5.1 Secure Data Exchange in Wireless Sensor Networks

An innovative PRE scheme is introduced in WSN to perform secured data communication between sensor nodes in wireless sensor network and data server. Different cryptographic schemes are used to improve the efficiency with minimum computational costs. PRE scheme is used for energy conservation with resource-limited sensor nodes. The designed scheme performed sophisticated key management and digital certificates to guarantee the secure key generation and distribution. PRE scheme is used to perform efficient authentication and scalable data sharing among different entities in WSN. The designed scheme preserved the sensor node data encryption with secured re-encryption tasks for reinforcing the data privacy and integrity. PRE scheme increased the security, efficiency, and network lifetime of WSN.

5.2 Energy aware and secure routing in WSN

An extended low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) is introduced to solve the energy scarcity and consumption problems. The clustering method is an efficient technique to minimize the energy consumption and to increase the network lifetime. Low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) is introduced to improve the energy efficiency through selecting cluster head (CH) on rotation through random integer technique. An extended LEACH is introduced to improve the network stability period. LEACH extension aimed on CH selection and not concentrated on secured communication. Blockchain integration and content validation in LEACH was used to detect malicious node through secure hash algorithm. An energy aware and secure routing (EASR) is introduced for hierarchical cluster based WSN. An improved threshold

value is used to choose the secure optimal CH and trust based routing model. EASR joined direct and indirect trust opinion values to limit the routing attacks for finding the trustworthy and reliable routes to the base station.

5.3 Optimization Assisted Model

A light weighted key distribution mechanism is introduced for safe and energy efficient communication in WSN. The designed model comprised the stages like optimal Cluster Head Selection (CHS), improved Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC)-based encryption and lightweight key management correspondingly. In first phase, hybrid optimization strategy termed Coot updated Butterfly algorithm with Logistic Solution Space algorithm (CUBA-LSS) is introduced for optimal clustering through choosing the optimal CH. The selection process depends on the consideration of Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), energy, delay, and distance. Data transmission is subsequent process for guaranteeing the secured transmission through Improved ECC. The lightweight key management system is established through session key generation to protect the encryption key.

5.4 Performance Metrics for Secured Data Transaction in WSN

The two performance metrics employed for secured data transaction is data confidentiality rate and packet delivery ratio. The data confidentiality rate is defined as the ratio of the number of data packets that are received by the base station in WSN. The data confidentiality rate is formulated as,

$$D_{CR} = \left[\frac{n_{AR}}{n} \right] * 100 \quad (3)$$

From (3), ' D_{CR} ' symbolizes the data confidentiality rate. ' n_{AR} ' indicates the data received by the base station. ' n ' symbolizes the total number of data packets considered as an input. The data confidentiality rate is measured in terms of percentage (%). Packet delivery ratio is calculated as the ratio of the number of data packets successfully

received at the sink node to the total number of data packets sent. The Packet delivery ratio is formulated as given below,

$$R_{PD} = \left[\frac{\text{Number of data packets correctly received}}{\text{Number of data packets}} \right] * 100 \quad (4)$$

From (4), R_{PD} denotes a packet delivery ratio. The packet delivery ratio is measured in terms of percentage (%).

Table 2 Tabulation for Data Confidentiality Rate and Packet Delivery Ratio for Secured Data Transaction in WSN

Parameters/ Methods	Data Confidentiality Rate (%)	Packet Delivery Ratio (%)
Innovative PRE scheme	94	91
EASR	91	94
Light weighted key distribution mechanism	95	97

Figure 3 Measurement Analysis of Data Confidentiality and Packet Delivery Ratio

Figure 3 illustrates the measurement analysis of data confidentiality rate and packet delivery ratio for three different existing methods, namely innovative PRE scheme, EASR and Light weighted key distribution mechanism. From the above graphical analysis, the red color column represents the packet delivery ratio of three different methods and green color column symbolizes the data confidentiality rate of three different methods. The performance of light weighted key distribution mechanism is higher than other two techniques. This is due to the application Coot updated Butterfly algorithm with Logistic Solution Space algorithm (CUBA-LSS) for optimal clustering through choosing the optimal CH. Lightweight key management system preserved the encryption key. The packet delivery ratio of light weighted key distribution mechanism is increased by 7% and 3% when compared to the innovative PRE scheme and EASR respectively. The data confidentiality rate of light weighted key distribution mechanism is increased by 1% and 4% when compared to the innovative PRE scheme and EASR respectively.

6. SECURED DATA AGGREGATION IN WSN

Wireless sensor networks have insufficient computational power and memory for different application. Data aggregation is the method of gathering the useful information from different location. Data aggregation is used to reduce the energy consumption. In WSN, secured data aggregation is a well-organized process with limited resources. Different methods are introduced for performing secured data aggregation in WSN. During data aggregation and transmission, security is an essential one to preserve the data against the intruders. The designed data aggregation is an expensive one and requires large amount of memory space at aggregator node (AN).

6.1 Secure and Long-Lived WSN for Data Collection

Energy minimization is an important task in WSN achieved through clustering process. Clustering in WSN is an efficient technique to increase the network lifetime. The main aim of the work is to improve the network lifetime with minimum node failures and

high packet delivery ratio. The hierarchical structuring process is carried out through clustering approach depending on data aggregation process. The aggregation process is carried out with two phases. The first phase performed the node arrangement in cluster using uniform distribution. The second phase described the cluster head selection and data aggregation using linear programming. The key aim was to reduce the energy consumption and increase the robustness of sensor network. Eventually the performance of the network will be evaluated in terms of low energy consumption, high packet deliveries and low congestions in the WSN.

6.2 Light-Weight Secure Aggregated Data Sharing

A lightweight Secure Aggregation and Transmission Scheme (SATS) are introduced for secured and lightweight data computation during the transmission. SATS presented the lightweight XOR operation for attaining the batch keys rather than expensive multiplication operation. AN Receiving Message Algorithm (ARMA) is introduced at the AN to aggregate the data generated by sensor nodes. Receiving Message Extractor (RME) algorithm is introduced to decrypt the message and execute the batch verification at Fog-Server. SATS preserved the against different security threats like denial of service attacks, man in the middle attack and reply attacks. SATS provides better storage capacity, computations cost, communications cost and energy consumption.

6.3 Energy Saving and Securing Data Algorithm

WSNs are categorized by diverse deployment because of low cost. WSNs are susceptible to different attacks. An efficient security solution is essential one to defend against attacks. The Energy Saving and Securing Data algorithm (ESSD) is introduced to minimize the energy consumption in data encryption and decryption. The designed algorithm is used for highly protected system for data. The key aim of robust and low-power encryption algorithm is to attain the data security during transmission. The designed algorithm is to examine the security algorithms like ECC and MD5. ESSD algorithm is introduced to provide the Message Digest 5 (MD5) computation simplicity through varying the Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) under power consumption.

6.4 Performance Metrics for Secured Data Aggregation in WSN

Data Aggregation Accuracy (DAA) is defined as the ratio of number of data points that are accurately aggregated and delivered to the base station. It is measured in terms of percentage (%). It is formulated as,

$$DAA = \frac{\text{Number of data points that are accurately delivered}}{\text{Number of data points sent}} * 100 \quad (5)$$

From (5), the accuracy is determined. When the accuracy level is higher, the method is said to be more efficient. Data integrity rate is defined as the number of data packets that have not been altered or modified by any attack nodes. The data integrity rate is determined as follows,

$$D_{IR} = \frac{\text{Number of data packets not altered by attack nodes}}{\text{Number of data packets}} * 100 \quad (6)$$

From (6), ' D_{IR} ' indicates the data integrity rate. It is measured in the unit of percentage (%). When the data integrity rate is higher, the method is considered as more efficient.

Table 3 Tabulation for Data Integrity Rate and Data Aggregation Accuracy for Secured Data Aggregation in WSN

Parameters/ Methods	Data Integrity Rate (%)	Data Aggregation Accuracy (%)
Hierarchical Structuring Process	92	91
SATS	94	93
ESSD	97	95

Figure 4 Measurement Analysis of Data Aggregation Accuracy and Data Integrity Rate

Figure 4 illustrates the measurement analysis of data aggregation accuracy and data integrity rate for three different existing methods, namely hierarchical structuring process, SATS and ESSD. From the above graphical analysis, the red color column denotes the data aggregation accuracy of three different methods and green color column symbolizes the data integrity rate of three different methods. The performance of ESSD is higher than other two techniques. This is because of using robust and low-power encryption algorithm to improve data security during transmission. ESSD algorithm provides the Message Digest 5 (MD5) computation simplicity through different Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) under power consumption. The data aggregation accuracy of ESSD is increased by 4% and 2% when compared to the hierarchical structuring process and SATS respectively. The data integrity rate of ESSD is increased by 5% and 3% when compared to the hierarchical structuring process and SATS respectively.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In the survey, energy efficient routing and secured data aggregation is carried out using nine different techniques. Different performance parameters are employed to

determine the energy efficient routing and secured data aggregation methods. When the result is compared with another study, energy efficient routing and secured data aggregation using optimization and cryptographic methods attained better results. Cryptographic methods attain the highest performance result than all the other existing secured data aggregation techniques. These results strongly suggest cryptographic and optimization methods can be implemented in future for energy efficient routing and secured data aggregation methods instead of the other conventional methods.

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